

On Ekeland Variational Principle in Asymmetric b-Metric Spaces

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Abstract

This paper extends the Ekeland Variational Principle (EVP) to the setting of asymmetric b-metric spaces, which generalize both asymmetric metric and b-metric spaces. By distinguishing forward, backward and bi-completeness, we establish corresponding forward, backward and bi-complete version of EVP. Examples are provided to demonstrate that forward and backward principles may yield different minimizers while the bi-complete EVP reduces to the classical EVP when symmetry holds. As an application, we obtain a forward and backward Cartisi-type fixed point theorem. These results broaden the scope of EVP and offer a new tools for optimization and fixed-point theory in asymmetric frameworks.

Keywords

fixed point, b-metric space, quasi-metric space, Ekeland variational principle, Cartisi fixed point.

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1. Introduction

Since its introduction in the 1970s by Ivar Ekeland [1], the Ekeland Variational Principle (EVP) has become a cornerstone of modern optimization theory and nonlinear analysis. The principle not only provides a variational characterization of approximate minimizers but also serves as a unifying tool for deriving fixed point theorems, Caristi's theorem, and critical point results in Banach space settings. Its applications span diverse fields including optimal control, equilibrium problems, convex analysis, and partial differential equations. Following Ekeland's original work, many generalizations of the principle have been established. Kirk [2] and Takahashi [3] extended EVP to complete metric spaces and normed linear spaces, while Borwein and Preiss [4] developed smooth variational principles applicable in infinite-dimensional settings. Wilson [11] introduced asymmetric metric spaces as quasi-metric spaces and Cobzaş [5] studied quasi-metric versions of the Ekeland variational principle and its connections with completeness properties of the underlying quasi-metric space. Farkas et al. [13] established a generalized variational

principle for b-metric spaces.

On another front, Bakhtin [6] introduced the concept of a b-metric space, where the triangle inequality is relaxed by a constant $s \geq 1$. This generalization has attracted considerable interest in fixed point theory, as shown in the works of Czerwik [7] and subsequent authors, leading to numerous results on contractive mappings, Caristi-type theorems, and variational inequalities in b-metric spaces. Bota, Molnár and Varga [8] investigated EVP in b-metric spaces and showed that the principle continues to hold under suitable completeness assumptions. Fixed point results in asymmetric metric spaces were studied by Khorshidvandpour et al. [14]. Recent developments in b-metric and asymmetric metric spaces can be found in [15, 16]. Studies in asymmetric b-metric (quasi-b-metric) spaces appear in [17, 18, 19].

Despite these advances, relatively little attention has been paid to asymmetric b-metric spaces, which combine both asymmetry and the relaxed triangle inequality. These spaces arise naturally in applications where distances are not symmetric and triangular estimates are approximate, such as computer science, decision theory, and models of directed networks. To the best of our knowledge, no systematic treatment of EVP in asymmetric b-metric spaces has yet been given.

Our work fills this gap by formulating and proving forward, backward, and bi-complete versions of the Ekeland Variational Principle in asymmetric b-metric spaces. In doing so, we unify and extend the previous lines of research: when the coefficient $s = 1$, our results reduce to the asymmetric metric setting, and when symmetry is imposed, we recover the classical EVP in b-metric and metric spaces.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1 (b-metric [6, 7]). *Let X be a non-empty set and $s \geq 1$ a real number. A function $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is called a b-metric provided that for all $x, y, z \in X$:*

$$(i) \quad d(x, y) = 0 \text{ if and only if } x = y,$$

$$(ii) \quad d(x, y) = d(y, x),$$

$$(iii) \quad d(x, z) \leq s(d(x, y) + d(y, z)).$$

A pair (X, d) is called a b-metric space.

It is clear that the definition of b-metric space extends the usual metric space; indeed if $s = 1$ we recover the classical metric space.

Example 2.1 ([9]). *The space $\ell_p(\mathbb{R})$ with $0 < p < 1$,*

$$\ell_p(\mathbb{R}) = \{(x_n) \subset \mathbb{R} : \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_n|^p < \infty\},$$

together with

$$d(x, y) = \left(\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} |x_n - y_n|^p \right)^{1/p},$$

is a b-metric space. By an elementary calculation we obtain that

$$d(x, z) \leq 2^{1/p} (d(x, y) + d(y, z)),$$

so one may take $s = 2^{1/p}$.

Definition 2.2 (Asymmetric metric [10]). *A function $d : X \times X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ is called an asymmetric metric and (X, d) is an asymmetric metric space if for all $x, y, z \in X$:*

$$(i) \quad d(x, y) = 0 \text{ if and only if } x = y,$$

$$(ii) \quad d(x, z) \leq d(x, y) + d(y, z).$$

Example 2.2 ([10]). *Let $\alpha > 0$. Define $d : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+$ by*

$$d(x, y) = \begin{cases} y - x, & y \geq x, \\ \alpha(x - y), & y < x. \end{cases}$$

Then d is an asymmetric metric on \mathbb{R} .

Definition 2.3. *Let ρ be an asymmetric metric on X . The conjugate of ρ is the mapping $\bar{\rho}$ defined by*

$$\bar{\rho}(x, y) = \rho(y, x), \quad x, y \in X.$$

The mapping

$$d_s(x, y) = \max\{\rho(x, y), \bar{\rho}(x, y)\} = \max\{\rho(x, y), \rho(y, x)\}$$

is called the symmetrized metric on X , and d_s is a metric on X if and only if ρ is an asymmetric metric on X .

Definition 2.4 (Forward/backward topology [10]). *The forward topology τ_+ induced by d is generated by forward open balls*

$$B^+(x, \varepsilon) = \{y \in X : d(x, y) < \varepsilon\}, \quad x \in X, \varepsilon > 0.$$

Likewise, the backward topology τ_- induced by d is generated by backward open balls

$$B^-(x, \varepsilon) = \{y \in X : d(y, x) < \varepsilon\}.$$

Definition 2.5 (Forward/backward convergence [10]). *A sequence $(x_n)_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is said to be forward convergent to $x_0 \in X$ if*

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_0, x_n) = 0,$$

and backward convergent to x_0 if

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} d(x_n, x_0) = 0.$$

We denote forward convergence by $x_n \xrightarrow{f} x_0$ and backward convergence by $x_n \xrightarrow{b} x_0$.

Definition 2.6 (Forward/backward completeness [10]). A space (X, d) is called forward complete (resp. backward complete) if every forward (resp. backward) Cauchy sequence in X forward(resp.backward) converges to a point in X .

Definition 2.7 (Forward/backward Cauchy [10]). A sequence $(x_k)_{k \in \mathbb{N}} \subset X$ is forward Cauchy if for every $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists N such that for all $m \geq n \geq N$, $d(x_n, x_m) < \varepsilon$. The sequence is backward Cauchy if for all $m \geq n \geq N$ we have $d(x_m, x_n) < \varepsilon$.

Definition 2.8 (Asymmetric b-metric / quasi-b-metric [17]). Let X be a non-empty set. A function $\rho : X \times X \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ is called an asymmetric b-metric (also called quasi-b-metric) on X if there exists a constant $s \geq 1$ such that for all $x, y, z \in X$:

- (i) $\rho(x, y) = 0$ iff $x = y$,
- (ii) $\rho(x, z) \leq s(\rho(x, y) + \rho(y, z))$.

Here s is called the coefficient of the asymmetric b-metric.

Remark 2.1.

- If symmetry is added, $\rho(x, y) = \rho(y, x)$, then ρ reduces to a standard b-metric.
- If $s = 1$, we get an asymmetric metric space.

So the hierarchy is

$$\text{metric} \subset \text{b-metric} \subset \text{asymmetric b-metric}.$$

Example 2.3. Define $\rho : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow [0, \infty)$ by

$$\rho(x, y) = (\max\{0, y - x\})^2 = (y - x)_+^2.$$

Then $\rho(x, x) = 0$, and in general $\rho(x, y) \neq \rho(y, x)$. One can check the b-triangle inequality with $s = 2$:

$$\rho(x, z) \leq 2(\rho(x, y) + \rho(y, z)),$$

by taking $\rho(x, y) = (\max\{0, y - x\})^2 = (y - x)_+^2$. This can easily be seen as $((z - x)_+)^2 \leq 2((z - y)_+^2 + (y - x)_+^2)$, hence (\mathbb{R}, ρ) is an asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s = 2$.

Theorem 2.1 (Classical EVP [1]). Let (X, d) be a complete metric space. Let $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be proper, lower semicontinuous and bounded below. Then for every $\varepsilon > 0$ and every $x \in X$ with

$$f(x) \leq \inf_X f + \varepsilon$$

and every $\lambda > 0$ there exists $y \in X$ such that

$$f(y) \leq f(x), \quad d(x, y) \leq \lambda,$$

and for all $z \neq y$,

$$f(z) > f(y) - \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda} d(y, z).$$

Theorem 2.2 (Caristi-type fixed point theorem [12]). Let (X, d) be a complete metric space and let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a mapping such that

$$d(x, Tx) \leq f(x) - f(Tx) \quad \text{for all } x \in X,$$

where $f : X \rightarrow [0, +\infty)$ is lower semicontinuous. Then T has at least one fixed point.

3. Results

Definition 3.1 (Forward/backward lower semicontinuity). A function $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ is forward-lsc if $x_n \xrightarrow{f} x$ implies

$$f(x) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n),$$

and backward-lsc if $x_n \xrightarrow{b} x$ implies

$$f(x) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n),$$

Theorem 3.1 (Forward Ekeland Variational Principle). Let (X, ρ) be a forward complete asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s \geq 1$. Let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, bounded below and forward-lsc. Fix $\varepsilon > 0$. Suppose $x_0 \in X$ satisfies

$$f(x_0) \leq \inf_X f + \varepsilon.$$

For every $\lambda > 0$ set $\alpha := \varepsilon/\lambda > 0$. Then there exists $x^* \in X$ such that:

- (1) $f(x^*) \leq f(x_0)$,
- (2) $\rho(x_0, x^*) \leq s\lambda$,
- (3) For every $y \in X$ with $y \neq x^*$,

$$f(y) > f(x^*) - \alpha \rho(x^*, y).$$

Equivalently,

$$f(y) + \alpha \rho(x^*, y) \geq f(x^*) \quad \text{for all } y \in X.$$

Proof. Fix $\lambda > 0$ and set $\alpha = \varepsilon/\lambda$. We construct inductively a sequence (x_n) as follows. Choose a summable sequence (ε_n) with $\varepsilon_n \downarrow 0$ and $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon_n < \infty$. Define for each $n \geq 0$ the perturbed functional

$$\varphi_n(y) := f(y) + \alpha \rho(x_n, y).$$

Choose $x_{n+1} \in X$ such that

$$f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq \inf_{y \in X} \varphi_n(y) + \varepsilon_n. \quad (1)$$

Putting $y = x_n$ in (1) gives

$$f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq f(x_n) + \varepsilon_n,$$

hence

$$\alpha \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq f(x_n) - f(x_{n+1}) + \varepsilon_n.$$

Therefore $(f(x_n))$ is nonincreasing and bounded below, so it converges to some $L \geq \inf_X f$. Summing the inequality from $n = 0$ to $N - 1$ yields

$$\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq f(x_0) - f(x_N) + \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \varepsilon_n.$$

Let $N \rightarrow \infty$. Since $f(x_N) \rightarrow L$ and $\sum \varepsilon_n < \infty$ we obtain

$$\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq f(x_0) - L + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon_n \leq \varepsilon + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \varepsilon_n < \infty.$$

Thus $\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) < \infty$ and $\rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow 0$.

Forward Cauchy property. For $m > n$, repeated use of the b-triangle inequality gives

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(x_n, x_m) &\leq s(\rho(x_n, x_{m-1}) + \rho(x_{m-1}, x_m)) \\ &\leq s(\rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) + \rho(x_{n+1}, x_{n+2}) + \dots + \\ &\quad \rho(x_{m-1}, x_m)) \\ &\leq s \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} \rho(x_k, x_{k+1}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for every $\eta > 0$ there exists N such that for all $m > n \geq N$ we have $\rho(x_n, x_m) < \eta$. Hence (x_n) is forward Cauchy. By forward completeness there exists $x^* \in X$ with $\rho(x^*, x_n) \rightarrow 0$ (i.e. $x_n \xrightarrow{f} x^*$).

Distance bound. For every m ,

$$\begin{aligned} \rho(x_0, x_m) &\leq s(\rho(x_0, x_1) + \rho(x_1, x_2) + \dots + \rho(x_{m-1}, x_m)) \\ &= s \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} \rho(x_k, x_{k+1}) \end{aligned}$$

Letting $m \rightarrow \infty$ and using the summability bound gives

$$\rho(x_0, x^*) \leq s \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \rho(x_k, x_{k+1}) \leq s \frac{\varepsilon + \sum \varepsilon_n}{\alpha}.$$

Choosing $\sum \varepsilon_n$ arbitrarily small and recalling $\alpha = \varepsilon/\lambda$ yields $\rho(x_0, x^*) \leq s\lambda$. Thus (2) holds.

Showing $f(x^*) \leq f(x_0)$. Since f is forward-lsc and $x_n \xrightarrow{f} x^*$ we get

$$f(x^*) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = L \leq f(x_0),$$

so (1) holds.

Variational inequality. From (1) with an arbitrary $y \in X$ we have

$$f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \leq f(y) + \alpha \rho(x_n, y) + \varepsilon_n. \quad (2)$$

Rearrange:

$$f(y) \geq f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha(\rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) - \rho(x_n, y)) - \varepsilon_n.$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$, using $\rho(x_n, x_{n+1}) \rightarrow 0$, $\rho(x_n, y) \rightarrow \rho(x^*, y)$ (by forward convergence of (x_n) to x^*), and $f(x_{n+1}) \rightarrow f(x^*)$, we obtain

$$f(y) \geq f(x^*) - \alpha \rho(x^*, y).$$

Hence $f(y) + \alpha \rho(x^*, y) \geq f(x^*)$ for all y . If equality occurs for some $y \neq x^*$ then by using inequality 3 and letting $n \rightarrow \infty$ gives equality in the limit. That is

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} ((f(y) + \alpha \rho(x_n, y) + \varepsilon_n) - (f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha \rho(x_n, x_{n+1}))) = 0. \quad (3)$$

Because each term x_{n+1} is an approximate minimizer of $\varphi_n(y)$, the only way the values at x_{n+1} and at y can be arbitrarily close is if the points themselves become arbitrarily close in the forward sense: $\rho(x_{n+1}, y) \rightarrow 0$, but we already have $x_{n+1} \rightarrow x^*$. So x_{n+1} would be converging to both x^* and y , forcing $y = x^*$, a contradiction. Therefore strict inequality holds for $y \neq x^*$, proving (3). \square

Corollary 3.1 (Backward EVP). *Let (X, ρ) be backward complete asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s \geq 1$. Let $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be proper, bounded below and backward-lsc. Fix $\varepsilon > 0$ and suppose $x_0 \in X$ satisfies*

$$f(x_0) \leq \inf_X f + \varepsilon.$$

For every $\lambda > 0$, set $\alpha := \varepsilon/\lambda > 0$. Then there exists $x^ \in X$ such that:*

$$(1) \quad f(x^*) \leq f(x_0),$$

$$(2) \quad \rho(x^*, x_0) \leq s\lambda,$$

$$(3) \quad \text{For every } y \in X \text{ with } y \neq x^*,$$

$$f(y) > f(x^*) - \alpha \rho(y, x^*).$$

Equivalently, $f(y) + \alpha \rho(y, x^) \geq f(x^*)$ for all y .*

Proof. The proof parallels that of Theorem 3.1 with the roles of arguments in ρ reversed: at each step one minimizes the backward-perturbed functionals and uses backward-Cauchy and backward completeness. The order of limits uses backward-lsc of f . \square

Theorem 3.2 (Bi-complete (symmetrized) EVP). *Let (X, ρ) be an asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s \geq 1$. Define the symmetrized metric*

$$d_s(x, y) := \max\{\rho(x, y), \rho(y, x)\}, \quad x, y \in X.$$

Assume (X, ρ) is bi-complete (i.e. (X, d_s) is complete). Let $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be proper, bounded below and lower semicontinuous with respect to d_s . Fix $\varepsilon > 0$ and suppose $x_0 \in X$ satisfies

$$f(x_0) \leq \inf_X f + \varepsilon.$$

Then for every $\lambda > 0$ there exists $x^ \in X$ such that:*

$$(1) \quad f(x^*) \leq f(x_0),$$

$$(2) \quad d_s(x_0, x^*) \leq s\lambda,$$

(3) For every $y \in X$ with $y \neq x^*$,

$$f(y) > f(x^*) - \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda} d_s(x^*, y).$$

Proof. Put $\alpha := \varepsilon/\lambda > 0$. For each $z \in X$ define

$$G_z(w) := f(w) + \alpha d_s(w, z), \quad w \in X.$$

Each G_z is d_s -lsc because f is d_s -lsc and $w \mapsto d_s(w, z)$ is continuous. By completeness of (X, d_s) any minimizing sequence for G_z is d_s -Cauchy and has a d_s -limit where the infimum is attained. Thus we may inductively choose a sequence (x_n) with x_0 given and, for each $n \geq 0$,

$$G_{x_n}(x_{n+1}) = \inf_{w \in X} G_{x_n}(w).$$

Putting $w = x_n$ in the minimization yields

$$f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) \leq f(x_n).$$

Hence

$$\alpha d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) \leq f(x_n) - f(x_{n+1}),$$

so $(f(x_n))$ is nonincreasing and bounded below and therefore convergent. Summing the inequality gives

$$\alpha \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) \leq f(x_0) - \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) \leq \varepsilon,$$

so

$$\sum d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) \leq \varepsilon/\alpha = \lambda \quad (4)$$

d_s -Cauchy and limit. For $m > n$, the the b-triangle inequality gives

$$d_s(x_n, x_m) \leq s \sum_{k=n}^{m-1} d_s(x_{k+1}, x_k)$$

Since the series of increments converges, the right handside tends to 0 as $n \rightarrow \infty$. Hence (x_n) is d_s -Cauchy. By completeness there exists $x^* \in X$ with $d_s(x_n, x^*) \rightarrow 0$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$.

From lower semi-continuity of f and monotonicity of $f(x_n)$, we get

$$f(x^*) \leq \liminf_{n \rightarrow \infty} f(x_n) = L \leq f(x_0),$$

so property (1) holds.

To show $d_s(x_0, x^*) \leq s\lambda$. Use the b-triangle inequality repeatedly: for every m ,

$$\begin{aligned} d_s(x_0, x_m) &\leq s(d_s(x_0, x_1) + d_s(x_1, x_2) + \dots + d_s(x_{m-1}, x_m)) \\ &= s \sum_{k=0}^{m-1} d_s(x_k, x_{k+1}) \end{aligned}$$

Letting $m \rightarrow \infty$ and equation (4) we obtain

$$d_s(x_0, x^*) \leq s \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} d_s(x_k, x_{k+1}) \leq s \cdot \frac{\varepsilon}{\alpha} = s\lambda.$$

Thus (2) holds.

Variational inequality. For arbitrary $x \in X$, the minimizer property yields for each n

$$f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) \leq f(x) + \alpha d_s(x, x_n). \quad (5)$$

Rearrange:

$$f(x) \geq f(x_{n+1}) + \alpha(d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) - d_s(x, x_n)).$$

Letting $n \rightarrow \infty$. Since $x_n \rightarrow x^*$ in d_s we have $d_s(x_{n+1}, x_n) \rightarrow 0$, $d_s(x, x_n) \rightarrow d_s(x, x^*)$, while $f(x_{n+1}) \rightarrow f(x^*)$. Passing to the limit in (5) we obtain

$$f(x) \geq f(x^*) - \alpha d_s(x, x^*).$$

Hence $f(x) + \alpha d_s(x, x^*) \geq f(x^*)$.

Strict inequality.

To see strict inequality when $y \neq x^*$, suppose $f(y) + \alpha d_s(y, x^*) \geq f(x^*)$ for some $y \neq x^*$. Then from (5) with $x = y$ equality must hold in the limit, forcing $d_s(x_{n+1}, y) \rightarrow 0$, but we already have $x_{n+1} \rightarrow x^*$ in d_s . So $d_s(y, x^*) = 0$, hence $y = x^*$ which is a contradiction. Therefore strict inequality holds for $y \neq x^*$, proving (3). \square

Corollary 3.2 (Reduction to classical EVP). *Let (X, ρ) be an asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s = 1$. Suppose ρ is symmetric (so $\rho(x, y) = \rho(y, x)$ for all x, y). Then $d_s = \rho$ is a complete metric on X . Let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, bounded below and lower semicontinuous with respect to ρ . Fix $\varepsilon > 0$ and suppose $x_0 \in X$ satisfies*

$$f(x_0) \leq \inf_X f + \varepsilon.$$

Then for every $\lambda > 0$ there exists $x^ \in X$ such that:*

$$f(x^*) \leq f(x_0), \quad \rho(x_0, x^*) \leq \lambda,$$

and for every $y \neq x^$,*

$$f(y) > f(x^*) - \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda} \rho(x^*, y).$$

Proof. If ρ is symmetric and $s = 1$ then $d_s(x, y) = \rho(x, y)$. Applying Theorem 3.2 with $d_s = \rho$ yields the classical Ekeland variational principle; the factor s disappears from the distance bound. \square

Example 3.1 (Forward vs Backward EVP selecting different minimizers). *Take $X = [0, 3]$ and define*

$$\rho(x, y) = \begin{cases} y - x, & y \geq x, \\ 2(x - y), & y < x. \end{cases}$$

Then ρ is asymmetric and satisfies the b-triangle inequality with $s = 2$:

$$\rho(x, z) \leq 2(\rho(x, y) + \rho(y, z)).$$

Define $f(x) = (x - 0.5)^2$ for $x \in [0, 3]$ and choose EVP parameters $x_0 = 2$, $\varepsilon = 2.25$, $\lambda = 2.25$ so that $\varepsilon/\lambda = 1$.

Forward penalized function. The forward penalized function is

$$g_f(y) = f(y) + \frac{\varepsilon}{\lambda}\rho(x_0, y) = (y - 0.5)^2 + \rho(2, y).$$

Compute $\rho(2, y)$:

$$\rho(2, y) = \begin{cases} 4 - 2y, & y \leq 2, \\ y - 2, & y \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

On $[0, 2]$,

$$g_f(y) = (y - 0.5)^2 + 4 - 2y, \quad g'_f(y) = 2(y - 0.5) - 2 = 2y - 3,$$

so the critical point is $y = 1.5$ and $g''_f(y) = 2 > 0$, hence $y = 1.5$ is the minimizer on $[0, 2]$. On $[2, 3]$ the function increases. Thus the global minimizer of g_f on $[0, 3]$ is $x^* = 1.5$.

Check the distance bound: $\rho(x_0, x^*) = \rho(2, 1.5) = 2(2 - 1.5) = 1 \leq s\lambda = 2(2.25) = 4.5$. Also $f(1.5) = 1 \leq f(2) = 2.25$ so $f(x^*) \leq f(x_0)$.

The forward variational inequality requires for $x^* = 1.5$ and any $y \neq 1.5$,

$$f(y) > f(1.5) - \rho(1.5, y).$$

or equivalently

$$\Delta(y) := f(y) - (f(1.5) - \rho(1.5, y)).$$

Computing $\Delta(y)$ separately on the two regions.

1. If $y > 1.5$; then, $\rho(1.5, y) = y - 1.5$. So $\Delta(y) := (y - 0.5)^2 - 1 + (y - 1.5) = y^2 - y + 0.25 - 1 + y - 1.5 = y^2 - 2.25$, so from $y > 1.5$, $y^2 > 2.25$, so $\Delta(y) > 0$
2. For $y < 1.5$; then, $\rho(1.5, y) = 2(1.5 - y) = 3 - 2y$. So $\Delta(y) := (y - 0.5)^2 - 1 + (3 - 2y) = y^2 - y + 0.25 - 1 + 3 - 2y = y^2 - 3y + 2.25 = (y - 0.5)^2 > 0$

Thus, the variational inequality holds strictly for every $y \neq x^*$. So the forward EVP conclusion holds and $x^* = 1.5$ is the forward EVP point.

Backward penalized function. The backward penalized function is

$$g_b(y) = f(y) + \rho(y, 2).$$

Compute $\rho(y, 2)$:

$$\rho(y, 2) = \begin{cases} 2 - y, & y \leq 2, \\ 2(y - 2), & y \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

On $[0, 2]$,

$$g_b(y) = (y - 0.5)^2 + 2 - y, \quad g'_b(y) = 2(y - 0.5) - 1 = 2y - 2,$$

so the critical point is $y = 1$ (with $g''_b = 2 > 0$). On $[2, 3]$ the function increases. Hence the global minimizer is $x_b = 1$. Checking the backward variational inequality shows $x_b = 1$ satisfies it strictly. Therefore the forward EVP and backward EVP select different minimizers (1.5 vs 1) for the same starting data.

Theorem 3.3 (Forward Caristi's theorem). Let (X, ρ) be an asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s \geq 1$ which is forward complete. Let $f : X \rightarrow \overline{\mathbb{R}}$ be proper, bounded below and forward-lsc. Let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a map satisfying the Caristi-type condition

$$\rho(x, Tx) \leq f(x) - f(Tx) \quad \text{for every } x \in X. \quad (6)$$

Then T has a fixed point.

Proof. Fix arbitrary $x_0 \in X$. Since f is bounded below, $\inf_X f$ is finite; choose $\varepsilon > 0$ and $\lambda > 0$ such that $f(x_0) \leq \inf_X f + \varepsilon$. Set $\alpha = \varepsilon/\lambda$ and apply the forward EVP (Theorem 3.1) to obtain $x^* \in X$ satisfying

$$f(x^*) \leq f(x_0), \quad \rho(x_0, x^*) \leq s\lambda,$$

and for every $y \neq x^*$,

$$f(y) > f(x^*) - \alpha\rho(x^*, y).$$

If $Tx^* = x^*$ we are done. Suppose $Tx^* \neq x^*$. Put $y = Tx^*$ in the variational inequality to get

$$f(Tx^*) > f(x^*) - \alpha\rho(x^*, Tx^*).$$

Rearrange:

$$f(Tx^*) + \alpha\rho(x^*, Tx^*) > f(x^*).$$

On the other hand, the Caristi condition (6) at x^* implies

$$\rho(x^*, Tx^*) \leq f(x^*) - f(Tx^*),$$

i.e.

$$f(Tx^*) + \rho(x^*, Tx^*) \leq f(x^*).$$

Because $\alpha > 0$ and $\rho(x^*, Tx^*) \geq 0$, the two inequalities contradict each other, hence $Tx^* = x^*$. Therefore T has a fixed point. \square

Corollary 3.3 (Backward Caristi's theorem). *Let (X, ρ) be an asymmetric b-metric space with coefficient $s \geq 1$ which is forward complete. Let $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ be proper, bounded below and forward-lsc. Let $T : X \rightarrow X$ be a map satisfying*

$$\rho(Tx, x) \leq f(x) - f(Tx) \quad \text{for every } x \in X.$$

Then T has a fixed point.

Proof. The proof follows by applying the backward EVP to the backward-perturbed functionals and duplicating the contradiction argument used in Theorem 3.3. \square

4. Conclusion

In this paper we established new extensions of the Ekeland Variational Principle within the framework of asymmetric b-metric spaces. By introducing forward, backward, and bi-complete versions of EVP, we showed that the asymmetry of the distance leads to distinct variational inequalities, which in turn may yield different minimizers. An illustrative example was provided to highlight the differences between forward and backward EVP.

As an application, we derived a forward and backward Caristi-type fixed point theorem in asymmetric b-metric spaces. These findings not only extend the scope of EVP beyond the existing results in metric, asymmetric-metric, and b-metric spaces but also provide new tools for optimization, equilibrium problems, and nonlinear analysis in asymmetric frameworks.

Future work may focus on developing multivalued and set-valued versions of EVP in asymmetric b-metrics, studying stability results, and exploring applications of variational inequalities in non-symmetric environments.

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